

ANALYZING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF HEPATITIS C PATIENTS. LITERATURE REVIEW**Zhanabayeva M.,***2nd year master's student in the specialty "Medicine", NJSC "Astana Medical University",
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Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10492302>**Abstract**

A literature review was conducted on the study of quality of life in patients with hepatitis C in global clinical practice based on data published to date. Viral hepatitis C is a serious global health problem that affects millions of people worldwide. In addition to physical symptoms, the disease can significantly affect the overall well-being and quality of life of patients. A number of studies are now available to shed light on various aspects of hepatitis C patients' lives that affect their physical health, psychological well-being and life satisfaction. The key point emphasized by most researchers is the need for a comprehensive approach to the treatment of patients, focusing not only on virus elimination, physical aspects of the disease, but also on adequate emotional support, disease awareness and the possibility of social integration to mitigate the negative impact on people's quality of life. Therefore, assessment of long-term quality of life in patients with hepatitis C at different stages of treatment and after virus elimination remains relevant at present.

Keywords: quality of life, viral hepatitis C, interferon-free therapy.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), today one third of the world's population is infected with hepatitis viruses [1].

Hepatitis C, along with HIV infection, tuberculosis, hepatitis B and a number of other infectious diseases, is a global medical and social problem [2].

The number of patients with chronic hepatitis C worldwide is about 58 million. About 1.5 million new cases of infection are reported annually. According to the WHO estimates, in 2019, approximately 290 000 people died from liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma as a result of hepatitis C virus infection [1, 3].

The all-round spread of infection and the uneven territorial distribution of morbidity, the latent course of the infectious process and the high frequency of its chronicity, as well as the active involvement of persons of reproductive and working age in the epidemic process determine the high socio-economic significance of hepatitis C [4, 5].

Over the last 5-6 years, serious progress has been made in the treatment of chronic hepatitis C, the main goal of which is to eliminate the virus. Today, according to various estimates, the effectiveness of therapy for chronic viral hepatitis C is 95-97%. However, taking into account the long-term chronic course of viral liver damage, combined with the negative impact of numerous psychological and social aspects, the study of the quality of life in this category of patients in the long term remains relevant at the present stage [6, 7, 8].

Purpose of the study

Analysis of literature data on the influence of modern methods of antiviral therapy for chronic hepatitis C on the quality of life of patients.

Materials and methods

A literature search was conducted in the electronic databases of PubMed, The Cichrane Library, Scopus. Inclusion criteria: reports on randomized and cohort studies, meta-analyses and systematic reviews; articles in the English and Russian languages. Exclusion criteria: materials with no evidence base, newspaper articles.

Results and discussions

Studying the quality of life in various diseases allows us to evaluate ongoing treatment and rehabilitation measures from the patient's perspective. According to WHO experts, quality of life is "an individual ratio of one's position in the life of society in the context of the culture and value systems of this society to the goals of a given individual, his plans, capabilities and the degree of general disorder" [1]. According to other definitions, quality of life is "a subjective indicator of the satisfaction of human needs, the degree of comfort of a person both within himself and within his society" [9].

Outpatient care for patients with hepatitis C affects various aspects of life, which determines the relevance of studying the quality of life in this category of patients [10]. To assess the impact of CHC (chronic hepatitis C) on QL (quality of life) and related socially significant problems, general tools and methods specific to this disease are used: the short form health survey 36 (SF-36); the European quality of life - 5 dimensions (EQ-5D-5L); the liver disease life quality assessment tool (LDQOL), etc. [11]. New approaches to measure fatigue as one of the main symptoms of manifestation of viral hepatitis C were described in their study by Gerber L.H. and his colleagues (2019). This group studying

chronic liver disease concluded that a number of questionnaires could be used to assess quality of life, such as: Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire (CLDQ), SF-36, Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS) [12].

According to numerous studies, it has been shown that the quality of life of patients with chronic viral hepatitis is significantly reduced in terms of physical and psychological components of health [13-16]. The same conclusion was reached by the authors of the study of quality of life of patients with chronic hepatitis using the EQ-5D-5L questionnaire. In the course of data collection and processing involving 100 patients on the basis of 2 polyclinics in Moscow and Tula with a confirmed diagnosis of CHC, Maksimova L.V. and Vorobyeva P.A. (2013) concluded that the majority of respondents (79%) have health disorders, with moderate pain or discomfort, mild anxiety or depression being the most common [17].

Honrubia López R. and colleagues (2020), evaluating the QL in 86 asymptomatic CHC patients and the control group, found no statistically significant differences in physical and psychological state as measured by the EQ-5D-5L (Table 1). It is worth noting that there was a positive dynamics in all the questionnaire indicators at the stages of treatment in the group of studied patients with CHC [18].

Using a similar questionnaire EQ-5D-5L (Table 1) and VAS (visual analogue scale), Spanish scientists Silvia Goñi-Esarte and his colleagues (2019) assessed the quality of life of 199 patients with CHC at weeks 12 and 48 after achieving sustained virological response (SVR) [19]. Analyzing the results, the researchers noted a gradual improvement in the quality of life in patients receiving interferon-free therapy. Thus, there was an improvement in 4 of 5 indicators of quality of life (mobility, daily activities, pain/discomfort, anxiety/depression) at week 48, in contrast to small changes in 3 indicators after week 12, which indicates the need for longer follow-up of patients with CHC. Improvements were more often observed in patients under 48 years of age, with fibrosis levels F2-F4, supporting the view that patients with F0-F1 have better QL data at baseline and require longer follow-up, as shown in several other studies [20, 21].

At the same time, the results of the study conducted by Canadian scientists (2023) show improvement in all EQ-5D-5L indicators (Table 1) between baseline, during the treatment phase (6 weeks from the start of therapy) and 12, 48 weeks after the completion of the course of direct-acting antiviral drugs in patients without cirrhosis (n=161). In the cohort of patients with cirrhosis (n=48), there were no statistically significant changes between baseline (pre-treatment) and 1 year after the antiviral therapy [22].

Table 1.

Descriptive results of the EQ-5D-5L questionnaire at different therapy stages

QL questionnaire	Authors/year	Number of patients / average age	Indicator	Before treatment	After treatment
EQ-5D-5L (Questionnaire of life quality assessment of the European life quality group)	GoñiEsarte S., Juanbeltz R., Martínez-Baz I., Castilla J., San Miguel R., Herrero J.I., Zozaya J.M., 2019	199 (52.3 (9))	mobility	35% (p = 0.002)	21%
			daily activities	26% (p<0.001)	11%
			pain/discomfort	60% (p < 0.001)	35%
			daily activities	4%	5%
			anxiety/depression	57% (p < 0.001)	35%
			VAS	70%	90%
	Honrubia López R., Madejón Seiz A., Romero Portales M., García Sánchez A., Castillo Grau P., Erdozain Sosa J.C., Oliveira Martín A., Robles A., García-Samaniego Rey J., 2020	86 (57.24 (11.52))	mobility	77.4% (p = 0.045)	86.1%
			daily activities	73.8% (p=0.61)	83.3%
			pain/discomfort	56.0% (p =0.19)	80.6%
			daily activities	73.8% (p= 0.66)	83.3%
			anxiety/depression	58.3% (p=0.35)	77.1%
			VAS	72.4%	82,7%
	Wong W.W.L., Wong J., Bremner K.E., Saeed Y., Mason K., Phoon A., Martel-Lafferrière V., Bruneau J., Feld J.J., Feng Z., Baguley E., Lee S.S., Powis J., Krahn M.D., 2023	209 (53.4 ± 11.6)	Cohort without cirrhosis (n=161)	0.79 ±0.17	0.84 ±0.15
			Cohort with cirrhosis (n=48)	0.69 ±0.28	0.71 ±0.23

One of the first studies to assess quality of life in the long term (more than 6 months after treatment) is “Direct antiviral agents for chronic hepatitis C virus infection improve health-related quality of life significantly in the long term” (2021). In their work, Mahmoud Atamla, Johad Khoury [24], studied the quality of life of hepatitis C patients using “The Liver Disease Symptom Index 2.0” (LDSI) life quality index questionnaire [25] in the period from January 2015 to August 2018 with more than 100 patients. The authors concluded that 7 of 9 parameters assessed, including itching, right upper abdominal pain, sleepiness during the day, anxiety about marital status, decreased appetite, depression, and anxiety about complications of liver disease showed significant improvement in the long term. The 2 assessed indicators such as joint pain and jaundice remained unchanged (Table 2).

Using a similar questionnaire, Egyptian scientists Youssef N.F., El Kassas M., Farag A., Shepherd A. (2017), assessed the quality of life in patients with CHC, having previously divided them into 2 identical groups with different therapy regimens (1 - sofosbuvir 400 mg + ribavirin 1000 mg /1200 mg, 2 - with the addition of peg-IFN for 24 weeks). There was a decrease in the QL indicators at the treatment stage in the group receiving triple therapy, which was probably due to the effect of the drug (peg-IFN), in contrast to the group with a dual treatment regimen, where positive dynamics was observed (Table 2). However, after the therapy completion, all indicators returned to the baseline level and no significant differences between the two groups were found [26].

Table 2.

LDSI 2.0 questionnaire results

QL questionnaire	Authors/year	Number of patients / average age	Before treatment	After treatment
LDSI 2.0 (The Liver Disease Symptom Index 2.0)	Mahmoud Atamla, Johad Khoury, Ihab Dabbah, Rimma Kramsky, Afif Yaacob, Ella Veitsmanand Tarek Saadi, 2021	100 (58.1±13.3)	1.22±0.95	0.29±0.47
	Youssef N.F., El Kassas M., Farag A., Shepherd A., 2017	62 (54.06 ± 10.41)	Dual therapy n=31(sofosbuvir 400 mg + ribavirin 1000 mg /1200 mg) 32.54 ± 21.23	26.60±17.01
			Triple therapy n=31 (+peg-IFN) 30.74 ± 17.67	37.53 ± 20.47

Kaminskaya S.N. (2014) in her study came to the conclusion that despite the fact that CHC is characterized by a low-symptom but progressive course, manifestations from the psycho-emotional sphere often become leading in the clinical picture. In her work, the author demonstrated various methods of psychological testing, depression assessment scales, as well as quality of life. Changes in the psycho-emotional sphere and a decrease in life quality (Table 3) were more pronounced in patients infected with 1B virus genotype. However, the use of modern combined antiviral therapy as part of the general complex treatment of CHC patients significantly reduced the identified psychopathological manifestations and improved the quality of life of this category of individuals [23].

A study aimed at assessing the long-term impact (1 year after the sustained virological response) of direct-acting antiviral drugs in the treatment of HCV on the quality of life of patients was conducted by Japanese scientists Akio Miyasaka, Yuichi Yoshida, Akiko

Suzuki, Yasuhiro Takikawa (2021). The instrument for studying QL in patients after HCV treatment was the short form eight-item questionnaire (SF-8). As a result of a survey of 109 patients with CHC, none of the SF-8 indicators differed significantly between baseline and 1 year after SVR24 (Table 3). Regarding age, sex, liver status and treatment regimen, only age influenced SF-8 scores 1 year after SVR24. In multivariable analysis, only age ≥ 65 years was significantly associated with physical component effects 1 year after SVR24. However, no significant factors were identified for assessing the mental component [27].

Similar studies using a different questionnaire (Short-Form-36) were conducted by Silvia Nardelli, Oliviero Riggio, Davide Rosati, Stefania Gioia (2019) and concluded that symptoms of depression and anxiety had a negative impact on the quality of life in patients with CHCV (Table 3). Treatment with direct-acting antiviral drugs to eradicate hepatitis C virus significantly improved neuropsychological symptoms [28].

Table 3.

**Scores of patients with CHC according to the SF-36, SF-8 questionnaires.
Baseline QL data and those after achieving SVR**

QL questionnaire	Authors/year	Number of patients / average age	Physical component		Psychological component	
			Before	After	Before	After
SF-36 (Medical Outcomes Study Short Form-36)	Kaminskaya S.N., 2014	62 (19-59 years)	69.2 ± 2.8	83.7 ± 4.7	50.6 ± 1.2	56.4 ± 1.4
	Wong W.W.L., Wong J., Bremner K.E., Saeed Y., Mason K., Phoon A., Martel-Laferrière V., Bruneau J., Feld J.J., Feng Z., Baguley E., Lee S.S., Powis J., Krahn M.D., 2023	209 (53.4 ± 11.6 years)	45.92 ± 10.54	48.35 ± 10.32	46.12 ± 12.82	49.66 ± 11.58
	Fagundes R.N., Ferreira L.E.V.V.C., Pace F.H.L., 2020	113 (58.69 ± 9.88)	47.77 (p<0.001)	57.10	48.27 (p = 0.04)	50.41
	Silvia Nardelli, Oliviero Riggio, Davide Rosati, Stefania Gioia, Alessio Farcomeni, Lorenzo Ridola, 2019	39 (59.8 ± 14.2)	62.8 ± 22.7	71.6 ± 21.2	59.8 ± 21.9	71.8 ± 19.1
	Ng X., Nwankwo C., Arduino J.M., Corman S., Lasch K.E., Lustrino J.M., Patel S., Platt H.L., Qiu J., Sperl J., 2018	255 (48)	53.34 ± 7.39		43.01 ± 8.61	
	Siqueira F.M., Ferreira V.L., Borba H.H.L., Pontarolo R., 2018	56 (57.4 ± 11.4)	56 (±66.4)	71.7 (±28.7)	59.9 (±24.5)	67.1 (±22.1)
	Ohlendorf V., Schäfer A., Christensen S., Heyne R., Naumann U., Link R., Herold C., Schiffelholz W., Günther R., Cornberg M., Serfert Y., Maasoumy B., Wedemeyer H., Kraus M.R., 2021	1180 (53.4)	48 (p<0.001)	50	40 (p<0.001)	45
	Kracht PAM, Lieveld F.I., Amelung L.M., 2018	68 (57)	43.2 ± 11.9	44.7 ± 10.9	49.2 ± 11.9	49.9 ± 12.6
SF-8	Akio Miyasaka, Yuichi Yoshida, Akiko Suzuki, Yasuhiro Takikawa, 2021	109 (67)	47.31 ± 7.94	46.96 ± 8.31	49.43 ± 6.88	49.72 ± 6.29

Several studies have examined QL in patients treated with direct-acting antiviral drugs and interferon-based regimens [29-31]. In particular, a study conducted by Ng X. et al. (2018) [32] demonstrated that interferon-free treatment regimens (elbasvir/grazoprevir) for CHC resulted in a significant improvement in QL indicators (Table 3) according to the questionnaire (SF-36), compared with the sofosbuvir/peg-IFN/ribavirin regimen.

A Brazilian study by Antóher (2018) assessed changes in QL using the SF-36 and CLDQ in a cohort of 56 patients with CHC treated exclusively with direct-acting antiviral drugs and found significant improvement in both tests after viral eradication [33].

At the same time, scientists Fagundes R.N., Ferreira L.E.V.V.C., Pace F.H.L. (2020) conducted a study to assess quality of life in 113 patients with CHC at different stages of therapy (Table 3). Results obtained 12 weeks after treatment were significantly better compared to baseline, weeks 6 and 12 of treatment. Among the 6 CLDQ domains assessed, 5 showed statistically significant increases: abdominal symptoms (p = 0.02), fatigue (p < 0.001), systemic symptoms (p < 0.001), activity (p < 0.001), and anxiety (p < 0.001) (Table 4). The emotional function did not reveal a significant difference (p>0.05) [34].

Table 4

CLDQ questionnaire scores depending on therapy regimen and fibrosis stage

QL questionnaire	Authors/year	Number of patients / average age	Indicator	Before treatment		After treatment				
				Compensated (n = 730)	Decompensation (n = 124)	Compensated (n = 730)	Decompensation (n = 124)			
CLDQ (Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire)	Siqueira F.M., Ferreira V.L., Borba H.H.L., Pontarolo R., 2018	56	abdominal pain	4.04 (± 1.78)		4.14 (± 1.74)				
			activity	4.26 (± 1.7)		4.32 (± 1.65)				
			fatigue	3.35 (± 1.65)		3.75 (± 1.64)				
			systemic symptoms	4.05 (± 1.33)		4.42 (± 1.14)				
			emotionality	3.55 (± 1.62)		4.01 (± 1.44)				
			anxiety	3.58 (± 1.65)		4.85 (± 1.31)				
			Total	3.81 (± 1.31)		4.25 (± 1.13)				
			abdominal pain	6.17		6.48				
			activity	6.24		6.84				
			fatigue	5.86		6.81				
			systemic symptoms	5.88		6.55				
			emotionality	5.52		5.88				
			anxiety	6.39		6.83				
			Total	5.99 (p<0.001)		6.63 (p<0.001)				
			CLDQ (Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire)	Fagundes R.N., Ferreira L.E.V.V.C., Pace F.H.L., 2020	113 (58.69 ± 9.88)	Cirrhosis	Compensated (n = 730)	Decompensation (n = 124)	Compensated (n = 730)	Decompensation (n = 124)
activity	4.95 ± 1.45	4.22 ± 1.34				5.43 ± 1.33	4.74 ± 1.40			
systemic symptoms	4.63 ± 1.33	4.06 ± 1.29				5.03 ± 1.33	4.42 ± 1.48			
emotionality	5.18 ± 1.29	5.00 ± 1.31				5.76 ± 1.16	5.34 ± 1.45			
anxiety	4.99 ± 1.38	4.51 ± 1.50				6.08 ± 1.11	5.68 ± 1.44			
Total	4.94 ± 1.21	4.45 ± 1.19				5.58 ± 1.11	5.05 ± 1.32			
Regimen 1: sofosbuvir + daclatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00					65.86 ± 24.1				
sofosbuvir + velpatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00					77.5 ± 20.5				
sofosbuvir + ledipasvir	64.1 ± 25.00					68 ± 0				
sofosbuvir + sofosbuvir + daclatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00					49.34 ± 29.9				
sofosbuvir + velpatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00					86 ± 0				
CLDQ (Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire)	Younossi Z.M., Racila A., Muir A., Bourliere M., Mangia A., Esteban R., Zeuzem S., Colombo M., Manns M., Papatheodoridis G.V., Buti M., Chokkalingam A., Gaggar A., Nader F., Younossi I., Henry L., Stepanova M., 2022	854				Regimen 1: sofosbuvir + daclatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		65.86 ± 24.1	
						sofosbuvir + velpatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		77.5 ± 20.5	
						sofosbuvir + ledipasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		68 ± 0	
CLDQ (Chronic Liver Disease Questionnaire)	Vyas B.H., Darji N.H., Rana D.A., Vyas K.Y., Malhotra S.D., 2021 [41]	31 (49.83 ± 13.81)				sofosbuvir + daclatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		49.34 ± 29.9	
			sofosbuvir + velpatasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		86 ± 0				
			sofosbuvir + ledipasvir	64.1 ± 25.00		86 ± 0				

A study of quality of life in 854 patients with liver cirrhosis as a result of CHC (730 - compensated, 124 - decompensated), conducted by Zobair M. Younoss and his colleagues (2021) for 3.5 years, shows improvement in all indicators according to CLDQ and SF-36 scores (Table 3, 4), with the exception of the psychological component in decompensated patients after the antiviral therapy. The gains in QL indicators were largely maintained at later time points in patients with compensated cirrhosis; however, starting at week 120, a decreasing trend was observed in the decompensated group. In addition, QL scores remained consistently lower in patients with decompensated cirrhosis compared to the compensated patients group [35].

Jean-Michel Pawlotsky, Christian B. Ramers (2020) used the same tool to assess the quality of life in patients with hepatitis C in their study, where they studied the effect of treatment on the improvement of patients' mental state before treatment and on average six months after. The results of the study prove that after successful treatment with direct-acting antiviral drugs, emotional well-being improved by 14%, while physical well-being did not change [36].

The results of the study conducted in a real cohort of patients (more than 1000) suffering not only from CHC infection (HIV co-infection, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), active injecting drug users, cardiovascular diseases, depression, etc.) were ambiguous. In their work Ohlendorf V., Schäfer A., Christensen S. "Only partial improvement in health-related quality of life after treatment of chronic hepatitis C virus infection with direct acting antivirals in areal-world setting-results from the German Hepatitis C-Registry (DHC-R)" (2021) studied the impact of modern treatment regimens on clinically important aspects of quality of life and confirmed that direct-acting antiviral drugs therapy leads to an overall improvement in quality of life in patients infected with hepatitis C. However, half of the patients did not achieve clinically significant improvement, and some of them even experienced a significant decrease in quality of life. In particular, the benefit of CHC treatment was particularly high in patients with initially critical life quality indicators (Table 3). The results may also indicate a greater impact of CHC treatment on mental health than on physical health. As an explanation, the authors suggest that the diagnosis of CHC itself leads to the development of mental health disorders due to stigmatization, isolation and discrimination, or the need to combat a potentially fatal infectious disease, uncertainty about the future. When the infection is cured, these concerns may disappear, which is likely to lead to an improvement in the mental aspect of QL [37, 38].

Authors from the Netherlands (2018) came to similar conclusions in their work, assessing the quality of life of 68 patients with HCV who underwent direct-acting antiviral drugs therapy immediately after treatment and 12 weeks after, and confirming that one of the predictors of a decrease in the mental aspect of QL (Table 3) is the use of different treatment regimens (ribavirin), obesity [39].

Thus, quality of life is a multidimensional concept; therefore, when identifying a decrease in QL, additional causes should be taken into account (chronic viral hepatitis B, D, HIV co-infection, alcoholic liver disease, etc.), possible therapeutic concepts and the level of QL before treatment. Direct-acting antivirals have revolutionized treatment with high rates of viral elimination and reduced health outcomes. A number of authors believe that further studies with longer follow-up are needed to optimize the quality of life of patients, which can contribute to increase their responsibility for their own health and the health of others, adequate perception of their own disease and optimal coexistence with it, prevention of social isolation and the best adaptation of patients in the conditions of modern society.

Conclusions

1. Analysis of the literature shows that viral hepatitis C has a significant impact on the quality of life of patients, including physical, psychological and social spheres. Changes in the psycho-emotional sphere and a decrease in quality of life were more pronounced in patients infected with 1B virus genotype.

2. Direct-acting antiviral drugs have revolutionized treatment by providing high rates of virus elimination and reducing health outcomes.

3. Improvement in indicators was more often observed in patients under 48 years of age, with fibrosis level of F2-F4, confirming the opinion that patients with F0-F1 initially have better QL data. The gains in QL were largely maintained at later time points in patients with compensated cirrhosis; however, starting at week 120, there was a decreasing trend in the decompensated group.

4. A number of authors believe that further studies with longer follow-up are needed to optimize the quality of life of patients, which can contribute to increasing their responsibility for their own health and the health of others, adequate perception of their own disease and optimal coexistence with it, prevention of social isolation and the best adaptation of patients in the conditions of modern society.

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